

**ДО ПИТАННЯ ЗБЕРЕЖЕННЯ ОБРАЗНОЇ СИСТЕМИ АВТОРА
ПРИ ПЕРЕКЛАДІ ТВОРІВ РУМУНСЬКИХ ПОЕТІВ /**

**ON THE ISSUE OF PRESERVING THE AUTHOR'S FIGURATIVE SYSTEM
WHEN TRANSLATING WORKS OF ROMANIAN POETS**

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The research presents the author's personal experience in the field of poetic translation from Romanian into Ukrainian. In the introductory section, the 30-year experience of bilingual and multilingual education of Ukrainians at the "Alec Russo" Balti State University is highlighted, along with the active collaboration of the university's Center for Ukrainian Language and Culture with institutions and organizations in Ukraine. This cooperation shaped the need for literary translation as one of the Center's areas of activity. The main part of the article highlights the experience of translating poetry by Moldovan and Romanian poets as part of a project by the Ministry of Education and Research of the Republic of Moldova aimed at translating current school textbooks into Ukrainian. As examples, translations of poems by poets Suceveanu, Vilcu, and Cosbuc intended for the textbook *Spiritual and Moral Education, Grade 2*, are presented.